

PEDAGOGICAL MODEL OF THE MUSICAL- EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN AN INCLUSIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Today many countries around the world allocate significant funds for the education and upbringing of citizens with limited abilities. One of the leading countries in the development of inclusive education is Italy, where children's residential institutions and boarding schools have not existed for nearly a century. Significant progress in this area is also observed in several other countries, including Finland, Sweden, and Cyprus

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Today, inclusive education is most highly developed in the United Kingdom. Less than 40% of individuals with disabilities study in closed, special-purpose schools. In 1998, the government announced an action program aimed at improving learning conditions for this group in schools and higher education institutions, as well as creating the most favorable opportunities for their future professional activities².

In 2002, the No Child Left Behind Act, approved by the U.S. Congress, also included music education³. Within the framework of this program, in the 1980s, the United States began the process of constructing new educational buildings and reorganizing existing ones, taking into account the diverse needs and abilities of students⁴.

Within the framework of the inclusive process, a special place is given to persons with disabilities and individuals with limited health capabilities. They face the greatest difficulties in socialization, and their ability to engage in communication is limited for several reasons: the presence of communication barriers; restricted mobility; insufficient interpersonal communication experience; lack of acceptance by society and limited opportunities for interaction; and the insufficient psychological readiness of parents of healthy students to accept children with disabilities in the same classrooms.

¹ Фуряева, Т.В. Педагогика интеграции за рубежом: монография / Т.В. Фуряева. Красноярск, 2005. 208 с

² Фуряева, Т.В. Педагогика интеграции за рубежом: монография / Т.В. Фуряева. Красноярск, 2005. 208 с

³ «Ни одного отстающего ребенка». Национальная образовательная программа США. [Электронный носитель]. URL: http://expert.ruobrazovatelnaia_politica (дата обращения: 11.11.19).

⁴ Ардзинба, В.А. Инклюзивное образование в США [Электронный документ] / В.А. Ардзинба. URL: <http://www.psyedu.ru> (дата обращения: 11.11.19).

There are two approaches to defining the essence of disability: the first is the medical approach, according to which functional impairments in health determine the attitude toward individuals by considering them ill, and improving their condition should be limited to medical rehabilitation measures⁵; The second is the social approach, in which attention is focused not on a person's diagnosis, but on the barriers that prevent them from fulfilling their needs. This makes it possible to consider the situation of learners from the perspective of ensuring equality for all citizens. Inclusive education aims to address emerging issues by creating a barrier-free environment and restructuring the education system, with special attention given to individuals with limited abilities.

One of the key tasks in ensuring successful inclusive education is fostering tolerance. Moral and virtuous principles form the basis of tolerant relationships within the community and friendly communication among students. Individuals with limited health capabilities or insufficient communication experience must feel the support and assistance of teachers and other members of the educational community.

The emergence of inclusive processes, including inclusion in the field of music education, has deep roots in the history of pedagogy. In particular, we know that general music education was introduced in the former socialist bloc countries of Eastern Europe. Music education in schools and colleges in the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and Japan is highly developed. Even in places where music education is among the subjects freely chosen by students, it often has a mass character and is provided free of charge to everyone. It is well known that choirs and orchestras in ordinary schools and colleges in the United States are capable of performing serious classical works, jazz compositions, and even entire musical productions. The experience of Italy is of particular importance, where more than 90% of students with special educational needs study in mainstream schools. This highlights that the financial support of partially inclusive schools is provided through state funding, private charitable contributions, and religious communities.

These traditions have strong historical roots. The great Italian composer A. Vivaldi lived and worked for many years at the "Ospedale della Pietà" in Venice — a women's monastery intended for abandoned children. Although some of the children there suffered from chronic illnesses, Vivaldi composed magnificent music for them and trained them as a teacher. Some of the pupils became famous musicians after leaving the shelter. Thus, the "Pietà" conservatory-shelter can be considered one of the earliest successful experiences of inclusive education. Although the maestro held the status of a priest, he was exempt from performing religious services due to asthma attacks, which influenced his worldview.

Such experience was widespread in other European countries as well, where music education became an important part of the educational and upbringing process. However, in the second half of the 18th century and throughout the 19th century, with the significant rise of secular culture, the messianic role of monasteries weakened considerably. This situation also affected the education of children with special needs.

Examples of comprehensive integration in the next historical period fall in the mid-20th century. They served as the basis for the development of inclusive processes in music education, symbolizing the humanization of everyday life. Notable examples can be drawn

⁵ Махсус педагогика / под ред. Н.М. Назаровой. М.: АCADEMA, 2000. С.11.

from the lives of world-famous musicians. Among them is the blind composer X. Rodrigo, author of the “Concierto de Aranjuez” for guitars and symphonic orchestra, as well as the visually impaired pianist R. Charles, who introduced us to the rich colors of jazz harmonies. An interesting case is the work of American saxophonist D. Sanborn, who suffered from severe asthma since childhood and relied on an oxygen mask. Following medical advice, he began playing wind instruments, which not only eased his life but also brought him worldwide fame. German bass-baritone singer T. Kvasthoff was born with a congenital disability. Thanks to fortunate circumstances and the support of teachers, he became a vocal professor at the Berlin University of Music and gained international recognition as the “king of the chamber stage.

These events are examples of “hidden inclusion,” where personal development arose from the courage and talent of musicians, the support of teachers, and certain positive circumstances. Each such example is a unique stroke of fortune. However, as the wise say, if a tree has branches, it must also have roots. Today, inclusive music education is widespread in Western Europe, the United States, and Japan, and in some cases, it produces remarkable results. Thanks to inclusion, there are individuals among musicians with disabilities who have achieved exceptional mastery and can be singled out for their outstanding accomplishments.

Violinist I. Perelman contracted polio at the age of four, yet this illness did not stop him from achieving his dream. He studied music at the academy in Tel Aviv and later at the Juilliard School in the United States. I. Perelman plays the violin while seated, which is unusual for soloists; he moves using a walker or a motorized wheelchair. Nevertheless, through music, he travels worldwide, astonishing audiences with his extraordinary skill and demonstrating human dignity, willpower and beauty.

Percussionist E. Gleni is also a unique and remarkable individual who has become a symbol of contemporary music. Although she nearly lost her hearing at the age of 11, with the support of her teachers, she graduated from the Royal Academy of Music in London and revolutionized the consciousness of many musicians worldwide. Following this event, significant changes occurred in educational institutions in the United Kingdom: “No one now has the right to reject applications solely because individuals have physical limitations... every person must be heard and have the opportunity to be admitted to an educational institution...”⁶.

This experience contributed to the emergence of a generation of “special” students in music education institutions in Europe, the United States, and Japan. These students completed their studies, became renowned professional musicians, and are successfully working in the field of high art. In this way, one of the most important goals of inclusion is achieved: providing individuals with limited learning opportunities access to the musical and cultural space, facilitating their socialization in society, and helping them adapt to life circumstances

References:

1. Фурьева, Т.В. Педагогика интеграции за рубежом: монография / Т.В. Фурьева. Красноярск, 2005. 208 с

⁶ Эвелин Глени учит слушать [Электронный документ]. URL: <http://youtu.be/8jU57PWq61g> (Электронная версия открытого урока) (дата обращения: 11.11.19).

2. "Ни одного отстающего ребенка". Национальная образовательная программа США. [Электронный носитель]. URL: [http:// expert.ruobrazovatel'naya_politica](http://expert.ruobrazovatel'naya_politica) (дата обращения: 11.11.19).
3. Ардзинба, В.А. Инклюзивное образование в США [Электронный документ] / В.А. Ардзинба. URL: <http://www.psyedu.ru> (дата обращения: 11.11.19).
4. Назарова Н.М. Махсус педагогика / под ред.. М.: АСАДЕМА, 2000. В.11.
5. Эвелин Глени учит слушать [Электронный документ]. URL: <http://youtu.be/8jU57PWq61g> (Электронная версия открытого урока) (дата обращения: 11.11.19).

